

Informed consent was obtained from all participants, with clear explanations provided regarding the nature, purpose, potential risks, and benefits of the study. Data confidentiality and participant privacy were rigorously maintained throughout the study. All personal information was anonymized, and data were stored securely to protect participants' identities.

Conflict of interest

The authors report no conflicts of interest.

Use of artificial intelligence

The authors confirm that artificial intelligence was not used in writing the work.

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EFFICACY OF USING THE MODIFIED HYSTEROSCOPIC METROPLASTY METHOD IN WOMEN WITH A HISTORY OF UTERINE SEPTUM AND RPL-SYNDROME

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Summary. Kalitsynska Yu. L., Gladchuk I. Z. **EFFICACY OF USING THE MODIFIED HYSTEROSCOPIC METROPLASTY METHOD IN WOMEN WITH A HISTORY OF UTERINE SEPTUM AND RPL- SYNDROME** - *The Odessa National Medical University; e-mail: ykalicinskaya@gmail.com*. **The aim:** to improve the results of treatment of women with RPL- syndrome associated with uterine septum (US) by modifying the technique of hysteroscopic metroplasty (HM). **Materials and methods.** The study involved 138 patients with uterine septum and RPL - syndrome in the anamnesis who were operated on between 2018 and 2023. The main group (I clinical) consisted of 88 patients in whom hysteroscopic metroplasty was performed according to the proposed modified technique. The comparative group (II clinical) consisted of 50 patients who were operated on according to the classical method of HM. The age of patients in both groups ranged from 19 to 40 years. The effectiveness of operations was assessed by questioning during consultations or by questionnaire data on pregnancy onset and its completion during the first year after HM. The formation of postoperative intrauterine adhesions (IUA) was also evaluated according to second-look hysteroscopy data in 3–6 months after HM in some patients. Statistical analysis of the results obtained was carried out using the program "Primer Biostatistics" (USA). **The results.** The proposed modified HM technique helps reduce the frequency of postoperative synechiae and severe forms of IUA after the procedure ($p<0.05$). In the main group, compared to the second group, the frequency of spontaneous miscarriages decreased by 3 times, the frequency of spontaneous pregnancies increased by 20%, and the total frequency of pregnancies and live births increased ($p<0.05$). **Conclusions.** The results obtained in the study indicate the expediency of implementation and use of the modified HM method.

Key words: uterine septum, hysteroscopic metroplasty, intrauterine adhesions, RPL-syndrome, infertility, Mullerian anomalies.

Реферат. Каліциньська Ю. Л., Гладчук І. З. **ЕФЕКТИВНІСТЬ ЗАСТОСУВАННЯ МОДИФІКОВАНОГО МЕТОДУ ГІСТЕРОСКОПІЧНОЇ МЕТРОПЛАСТИКИ У ЖІНОК З ПЕРЕГОРОДОЮ МАТКИ ТА RPL-СИНДРОМОМ В АНАМНЕЗІ.** **Мета:** покращити результати лікування жінок з RPL-синдромом, асоційованим з ВМП шляхом модифікації методики гістероскопічної метропластики. **Матеріали і методи.** В дослідженні приймали участь 138 пацієток з внутрішньоматковими перетинками та RPL-синдромом в анамнезі, які були прооперовані в період із 2018 по 2023 рр. Основну групу (I клінічна) склали 88 пацієток, у яких гістероскопічна метропластика виконувалась згідно запропонованої модифікованої методики. Порівняльну групу (II клінічна) становили 50 пацієток, які були прооперовані за класичним способом ГМ. Вік пацієнтів в обох групах коливався у межах 19–40 років. Ефективність операцій оцінювалася шляхом опитування під час консультацій або за даними анкетування щодо настання вагітності та її завершення протягом першого року після ГМ. Також проводилась оцінка формування післяопераційних внутрішньоматкових сінехій за даними second-look гістероскопії через 3–6 місяців після ГМ у частини хворих. Статистичний аналіз отриманих результатів проводили з застосування програми “Primer Biostatistics” (USA). **Результати.** Запропонована модифікована методика ГМ сприяє зменшенню частоти виникнення післяопераційних сінехій та важких форм ВМС після проведеної процедури ($p < 0.05$). В основній групі в порівнянні з другою групою частота спонтанних викиднів зменшилась в 3 рази, збільшилась частота спонтанних вагітностей на 20% та збільшилась загальна частота вагітностей та живонароджень ($p < 0.05$). **Висновки.** Отримані результати дослідження вказують на доцільність імплементації та застосування модифікованого способу ГМ.

Ключові слова: внутрішньоматкова перетинка, гістероскопічна метропластика, внутрішньоматкові сінехії, RPL-синдром, безпліддя, невиношування, мюллерові аномалії.

The uterine septum is the most common abnormality in the development of female genital organs. Its frequency ranges from 1 to 3% in the population, and in the women with a history of miscarriage and infertility, the frequency of US detection is 5.5-24.5% [1, 2]. According to most authors, hysteroscopic metroplasty (HM) is considered to be the main method of treatment for women with RPL- syndrome associated with uterine septum. It is aimed at removing the membrane itself and restoring the normal anatomy of the uterine cavity using various operative techniques: mechanical, laser and, most frequently, electrosurgical [3-5]. However, the main disadvantage of these methods is the risk of intrauterine adhesions (IUA) forming in the postoperative period, which reduce the effectiveness of surgical intervention and sometimes they not only do not improve a woman's reproductive prospects, but also lead to their deterioration, or even to their complete loss [6]. Therefore, it is obvious that the improvement of the immediate and long-term results of HM is, among other things, related to the improvement of the surgical technique of operative intervention and the development of new, more effective methods. Based on the analysis of the literature and our own experience, we developed a method of surgical treatment of uterine septum of the class U2a (ESHRE/ESGE) in the women with RPL-syndrome, which showed positive results concerning prevention of the formation of postoperative intrauterine adhesions and improvement of the reproductive function [copyright of the method No123177 of 01/24/2024 "Modified method of hysteroscopic metroplasty according to I.Z. Gladchuk, V.I. Gladchuk and Kalitsynska Yu.L."]. [7].

The aim of the paper is to improve the results of treatment of the women with RPL-syndrome associated with US by modifying the technique of hysteroscopic metroplasty.

Materials and methods

The results of treatment of 138 patients with IUM and a diagnosis of RPL-syndrome, who were treated in the gynecological department of the Medical Center of ONMedU between 2018 and 2023, and who underwent hysteroscopic metroplasty, were analyzed. According to the study design, two experimental groups were formed. The main group included 88 (52.7%) patients with

US, for whom the modified HM technique was applied. The control group included 50 patients who were operated on according to the classic HM method. The age of patients in both groups ranged from 19 to 40 years. The average age of the women in the main group was 27.52 ± 1.59 years, in the comparison group - 28.21 ± 1.65 ($p > 0.05$). The follow-up period was 1 year.

The preoperative predictors that were investigated during the conducted work did not differ statistically in two clinical groups and did not affect the quality and results of the parameters studied (Table 1). Inclusion criteria for the study: age from 19 to 40 years and the presence of US class U2a (according to the ESHRE/ESGE classification) with an established diagnosis of primary miscarriage (RPL-syndrome) and/or premature birth. Exclusion criteria were women with clinically insignificant septum, without a history of RPL-syndrome who had complete class U2b, cervical and vaginal anomalies, as well as patients who required repeated hysteroscopic metroplasty.

Table 1

Comparative characteristics of the studied preoperative predictors in women of two clinical groups (n=138)

Investigated indices	Main group (n=88)		Comparison group (n=50)		Statistical evaluation
	Absolute n	%	Absolute N	%	
Age of patients (years)	27.52±1.59		28.21±1.65		t- Student's test p>0.05
Number of pregnancies in the history:					Z is a criterion for comparing two proportions
2	56	63.6±0.55	33	66.0±0.95	Z=-0.098 p=0.922
3	22	25.0±0.49	13	26.0±0.88	Z=-0.074 p=0.941
> 3	10	11.4±0.36	4	8.0±0.37	Z=-0.342 p=0.732
AUB (Abnormal uterine bleeding)	10	11.36±0.36	5	10.0±0.60	Z=-0.038 p=0.97
Endometrial polyposis/hyperplasia	26	29.5±0.52	14	28.0±0.90	Z=-0.142 p=0.172
EGE (External genital endometriosis)	12	13.6±0.39	7	14.0±0.69	Z=-0.192 p=0.848
PCOS (Polycystic ovary syndrome)	14	15.9±0.42	7	14.0±0.69	Z=-0.052 p=0.958
Uterine myoma	8	9.1±0.33	4	8.0±0.54	Z=-0.094 p=0.925
Membrane size 1/3	53	60.2±0.56	32	64.0±0.96	Z=-0.259 p=0.796
½	26	29.5±0.52	14	28.0±0.90	Z=-0.008 p=0.993
2/3	9	10.22±0.34	4	8.0±0.48	Z=0.126 p=0.900

This study uses HM technique proposed by the authors of the paper [7]. The presented modified method of HM differs from the classic electrosurgical method in the fact that HM according to the modified method is performed on the 10th-12th day of the menstrual cycle, while according to the classic method, the operation is performed immediately after menstruation or immediately after scraping the mucous membrane of the uterine cavity. After dilating the cervical canal and inserting a 9 mm hysteroscope (Karl Storz, Germany) to achieve adequate visualization, the uterine cavity is inflated with the saline of sodium chloride. After revision of the uterine cavity

and evaluation of the type of US, the septum dissection is performed using the bipolar operative technique. Unlike the classic method, which consists only in dissecting the septum with an L-shaped or loop bipolar electrode, starting from the midline, the modified technique uses a combined incision-excision technique. An L-shaped electrode is used for dissection of the endometrium before the appearance of the underlying fibrous tissue of the thick septum, and a 5-mm loop bipolar electrode is used for excision of the thick septum. Resection (excision) is stopped when, in the panoramic view, the tube angles are visualized at the same level. The final stage of the proposed method consists in endoscopic curettage of the endometrium with a "cold" loop electrode followed by its endoscopic autotransplantation to the wound surface of the uterine cavity, which aims to improve reparative processes on the newly formed wound surface.

All operations were performed under intravenous anesthesia in hospital conditions without additional preoperative hormonal therapy. Antibiotic prophylaxis and postoperative additional procedures for the prevention of IUA were not prescribed to none of the study groups.

During all operative interventions, the amount of injected and withdrawn distention fluid was measured to prevent its excessive absorption.

The effectiveness of surgery was assessed by questioning during consultations or by questionnaire data as to the onset of pregnancy and its completion during the first year after HM. An evaluation of the postoperative formation of intrauterine adhesions was also carried out according to second-look hysteroscopy after 3–6 months after HM in some patients.

The study was conducted in compliance with moral and ethical principles in accordance with the main provisions of Helsinki Declaration of the World Medical Association of biomedical research where a person is their object (World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki 1994, 2000, 2008), according to the positive conclusion of the Commission of Bioethics of Odessa National Medical University of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine (Minutes No32 of 06/14/2021).

Statistical processing of the study results was carried out using "Primer Biostatistics" program (USA). The average arithmetic value (M) and the error of determining the average value ($\pm m$) was used to analyze the indices. The probability of differences in parametric characteristics in groups was assessed using the Student's test (t-test). During the calculations, statistically significant differences were considered at $p < 0.05$ (99% confidence level (CL))

Results and discussion

According to most authors, hysteroscopic metroplasty is considered to be an optimal method of treatment of patients with US. However, there is still no single unified opinion regarding the need for surgical treatment of US. [8-10].

Analyzing the structure of negative consequences in the postoperative period, we came to the conclusion that formation of the most frequent complications should be attributed to postoperative IUA. According to the literature, IUA occur on an average in 40% of patients after various intrauterine manipulations and there is decreasing trends [11,12]. There is no doubt that the effectiveness of tissues regeneration after their damage in the process of HM directly depends on surgical technique applied, level of surgical technique and conditions for its implementation. In two clinical groups, HM was performed by experienced doctors, level of surgery technique of whom corresponds to the highest qualification category and could not significantly affect the parameters under study.

In 40 patients of the main group and in 27 patients of the comparison group a second-look hysteroscopy was performed in 3–6 months in the presence of various indications. Degree of IUA severity was evaluated according to the classification proposed by Manchanda's Endoscopic Center (MEC), India [13]. General index of frequency of the postoperative IUA formation was $17.5 \pm 0.95\%$ ($n = 7$) in the main group, of which IUS of the first degree of severity was recorded in 6 patients ($15.0 \pm 0.88\%$), and II degree – in only 1 patient ($2.5 \pm 0.38\%$) (Table 2). Severe synechiae in the main group were not diagnosed. In the comparison group the formation of postoperative IUA was observed in 12 ($40.7 \pm 1.85\%$) patients. IUA of the 1st degree was formed in 6 patients ($19.0 \pm 1.48\%$), II degree adhesions – in 5 women ($11.9 \pm 1.46\%$) and III degree of severity - in 4 ($9.5 \pm 1.34\%$).

We can assume that the results obtained are associated primarily with peculiarities of conducting a modified HM. According to the classic method HM is performed immediately after menstruation, in the early proliferative phase, or not infrequently after preliminary scraping of the

mucous cavity of the uterus for the purpose of better visualization of the cavity, which can significantly worsen the postoperative regeneration of the mucous membrane lining of the uterus and thereby provoke the formation of IUA. In our opinion it is advisable to perform HM on the 10-12th day of the menstrual cycle, at the physiological stage of hyperplasia when the endometrium has the best characteristics for its autotransplantation to the postoperative area for better healing and recovery in the postoperative period. This approach affects the reduction of the postoperative IUA formation and improves the period of implantation in the future, which our study demonstrates.

Table 2

Comparative characteristics of the severity of IUA in 3–6 months after HM performance in participants under study (n = 67)

Degree of IUA severity (by classification of MES)	Main group (n=40)		Comparison group (n=27)		Statistical evaluation
	Absolute N	M+m,%	Absolute N	M+m,%	
I	6	15.0±0.88	6	19.0±1.48	Z=0.429 p=0.668
II	1	2.5±0.38	5	11.9±1.46	Z=1.814 p=0.07
III	0	0	4	9.5±1.34	Z=2.041 p=0.041
Total	7	17.5±0.95	12	40.7±1.85	Z=2.120 p=0.034

In case of excessive traumatization of the endometrium during surgery, the risk of postoperative intrauterine formation increases significantly, which worsens reproductive expectations. According to the published data of Hua et al and Agostini et al (2011) the presence IUA was associated with a 6-fold increased risk of preterm birth and premature rupture of amniotic membranes 3 times, increasing frequency of childbirth by the caesarean section [14, 15].

Reproductive results were studied in 96 patients who tried to conceive after HM during the first year (61 patients from I clinical group and 35 patients from II clinical group). The other 42 patients were excluded from the study for various reasons, in particular, due to refusal of trying to conceive (Tabl. 3). First of all, while using the improved HM technique a decrease in frequency of miscarriages is observed almost 3 times - 9.6% compared to the classical method of 33%, which contributes to an increase in the overall level of live birth in the first clinical group - 47 (90.4%) compared to the classic incision technique - 66.7% (p<0.05). According to the data of our studies, the frequency of term births in the women who underwent HM by the modified method, was significantly different from this indicator in the comparison group by almost 30% (p>0.05). In addition, the number of premature births in the main group was smaller but the difference was not statistically significant (p>0.05). Since US consists of the fibromuscular tissue and has a reduced blood supply, this can lead to poor implantation and loss of pregnancy in the early terms. At later stages of gestation, the septum reduces the space for development of the fetus, which leads to miscarriage, incorrect position of the baby or premature births [16, 17]. The developed hysteroscopic technique of metroplasty, which is based on the use of incision-excision technique makes it possible to remove completely the tissue of the intrauterine membrane. We assume that this approach contributes to the maximum reconstruction of the uterine cavity in contrast to the classic technique, where only the dissection of US is performed.

There is a noticeable difference in the overall frequency of pregnancies in the examined groups. In 52 cases pregnancy was recorded using the improved HM technique in the first clinical group, compared to the classical incisional technique – 24 cases (p<0.05). A statistically significant difference between the groups was also found in the method of pregnancy, namely in 36 (69.2%) women of the I clinical group pregnancy occurred independently, and 16 (30.8%)

women became pregnant through IVF, unlike II clinical group, in which 10 (41.7%) spontaneous pregnancy cases were observed and 14 (58.35%) cases with the help of reproductive technologies ($p < 0.05$). Due to the burdensome anamnesis and reconstructive plastic surgery, the majority of women in both clinical groups gave birth by the cesarean section, however, 9 women in the first clinical group and 3 women from the comparison group gave birth physiologically ($p > 0.05$) (Table 3).

At this stage of the study, the proposed method of treatment of US already has advantages over standard operations, but it requires further, more in-depth studies.

The results of the conducted study indicate the expediency of implementing and using a modified method of HM and thereby create prospects for further study of the causes and mechanisms of the development of RPL - syndrome in women of reproductive age with US.

Table 3

Comparative characteristics of reproductive consequences after HM in both clinical groups (n=76)

Results	I (n=52)		II (n=24)		P
	n	%	n	%	
Independent pregnancy	36	69.2	10	41.7	P<0.05
IVF	16	30.8	14	58.3	P<0.05
Result of pregnancies					
Urgent childbirth	40	76.9	12	50	P<0.05
Premature birth	7	13.5	4	16.7	P>0.05
Miscarriage	5	9.6	8	33.0	P<0.05
General live birth	47	90.4	16	66.7	p<0.05
The path of birth	47		16		
Independent childbirth	9	19.1	3	18.75	P>0.05
Cesarean section	38	80.9	13	81.25	P>0.05

Conclusions

1. The proposed modified HM technique helps to reduce the frequency occurrence of postoperative synechiae and severe forms of IUA after the procedure ($p < 0.05$).

2. The application of the modified method of hysteroscopic metroplasty in women with RPL - syndrome compared to classical HM helps to reduce the frequency of spontaneous miscarriages by 3 times, is accompanied by an increase in the frequency of spontaneous pregnancies by 20% and an increase in the overall frequency of pregnancies and live births.

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Внесок авторів / authors' contribution

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Доступність даних/Data Availability

Дані будуть надані за обґрунтованим запитом

Заява про поінформовану згоду /Informed Consent Statement

Від пацієнтів було отримано письмову поінформовану згоду на обробку персональних даних та їх подальше використання.

Конфлікт інтересів /Conflicts of Interest

Автори заявляють про відсутність конфлікту інтересів

Використання штучного інтелекту / Use of artificial intelligence

Автор підтверджує, що під час написання роботи ШІ не використовувався

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